

Comparison of clinical placement in Bachelor of Science in nursing internees of public and private institutions based on Pakistan nursing council guidelines

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ABSTRACT: Background: The aim of the study to compares clinical placements of BS Nursing internees in public and private sector institution based on Pakistan Nursing Council internship policy as mandatory for license;

Methods and Material: The study was conducted in Islamabad, Lahore, and Peshawar 187 internees who had undergone clinical placement during the year 2022–2023, Data was gathered using researcher self-made questionnaire to assess and compare clinically affiliated Hospital and internees' socio-demographic data, pattern of the placement and perception of the interns.

Design: This is Comparative Descriptive study.

Results: The study indicates that there is a higher number of female interns in Private Sector Hospitals in the Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) compared to KPK Private Sector College male internees 27.3% struggled to find clinical placements after BS Nursing graduation, with only 1.1% following the Nursing Council guidelines. The majority (44.9%) did not receive remuneration (Paid Internship) and had difficulties during their internship year. Ineffective supervision and inadequate feedback hindered professional learning facilities and scope of work.

Conclusion: The study suggests that future internship program planning, assessment, monitoring, and surveillance can be improved, particularly for institutions lacking clinical placements, as the compulsory clinical placements inclusively unvivid and compromised.

Keywords: Internees, Clinical Placement. Nursing Council, Mandatory, Remuneration

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1. Introduction

Clinical Placement (Internship) is an obligatory training year for all bachelor nursing graduates according to Pakistan Nursing Council Rules as mandatory for license, it allow students to observe and participate in real-life health care situations, Clinical placements are valuable opportunities for internees to apply theoretical knowledge in a real-world setting, Contemporary Nursing science is founded on theoretical teaching through the classroom and practical teaching through laboratory simulation and clinical settings (Hashemiparast et al., 2019; Pattison et al., 2022). In Saudi Arabia, nursing students are required to complete up to 75 credit hours of practical experience (Aljohani, 2020). Practical learning occurs during clinical training in different healthcare settings, such as hospitals, primary care centers, elderly centers, and rehabilitation centers. Educational institutions are tasked with evaluating the educational process, whether theoretical or practical (Asadzaker et al., 2015).

Background

Nursing interns' clinical placement year is insufficient to fully characterise the issues and barriers related to institutional placement at the national and international levels that they encountered within the clinical learning environment [5]. It's not always easy to go from the student stage to the professional stage of life. When they start working, students confront a variety of difficulties. Students can be helped to develop their abilities by integrating conceptual knowledge and training through academic and clinically-oriented internship programmes. As to investigate deeper into the issues surrounding clinical placements, our discussion will highlight the similarities and differences between public and private organizations to better understand their impact on with the professional development of future nurses in Pakistan.

Clinical placement may significantly impact the caring abilities of nursing professionals. However, there is a lack of comprehensive assessment of undergraduate nursing internee's placement program (Public/Private Sector) institutions based on Nursing Council guidelines and their role in shaping students' skills, confidence, and competence as future healthcare professionals.

I would argue that Adherence to PNC guidelines significantly enhances clinical placement quality, promoting better learning outcomes for nursing interns through practical evidence and observations. In the beginning, clinical observations, practical exams, and written practical examinations were utilized to evaluate a nurse's ability, according to Lauri et al. Nursing preparation included both learning theory and using it in patient care. It involves assessing a nurse's personality attributes, including their values, skills, judgement, and attitude.

The clinical skills training in nursing education has to be examined, according to Sharif and Masoumi. Additionally, these researchers observed in their study that nursing students had worries about the theory-practice gap, clinical supervision, professional obligations, and clinical anxiety. Therefore, efforts to bridge the gap between theories and practice in order to support professional development in a work environment that emphasises action may be helpful. The development of capable and self-assured new graduate nurses who stay in the hospital is a significant problem [6].

When it comes to clinical placement, the questions arise whether training institute (Private/Public) may hold the Internship Program at their own affiliated hospital and whether the Hospital offering clinical placement may stick to Pakistan Nursing Council policies. The Pakistan Nursing Council, a regularity body for nursing education and practices perceived that most of the institutions providing placement do not follow the Council's guidelines, and that nurse training institutes without their own teaching hospitals fail to place their students in the mandatory one- year clinical placement.

2. Methods and Material

Aim of the Study

To assess and compare the of Bachelor of Science Nursing internee's clinical placement, using The Placement assessment Tool (PAT) at various nursing institutions that have been given recognition by regulatory/affiliating body.

Research Study Design

This is comparative descriptive study.

Research Study Setting

Private and Public Sector Institutions placement and training Institutions Internees across the variety of hospitals at Islamabad Capital territory (ICT), Lahore and Peshawar, Pakistan. The placement duration is ranged from 1 to 09 months

Duration of Study

The study was completed in nine (09) months period after the approval of Research Ethical Committee (REC), University of Lahore. Pakistan. during these period data was collected employed purposive data collection technique were used.

Population and Sample Size of the research Study

The population of interest was Bachelor of Nursing internees at Private and Public Sector Institutions placement and training Institutions. The inclusion criteria include: (1) Nurses successfully completed placement programme within last two years, (2) Interns who are placed in a six-month to one-year clinical internship placement program. 169 or more measurements are needed to have a confidence level of 95% that the real value is within $\pm 5\%$ of the measured/surveyed value. since this is a survey design with no intervention. The probability for a type one Margin of error: 2.92% yielding confidence level 0.99.

Review and Validity of Data Tool

Researchers reviewed 190 items ((mean years of experience more than 15 years and as nurse registration – 20-years and above), removing duplicates and non-applicable statements, and an expert panel rated relevance and clarity, producing and selecting items from other generic training evaluation tools.

Research Data Tool

The Clinical Placement Assessment Tool, developed by the researcher and expert review, was used to measure internees' socio-demographic placement and perception of their clinical placement experience.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling method was used to select samples from the overall sample size based on the study's judgment, assessing sample with specific characteristics.

Ethical Consideration

The University of Lahore Research Ethical Committee and Head of Nursing institutions approved data collection, ensuring voluntary participation and consent through questionnaire return, as per University of Lahore's rules and regulations.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data collection was checked for missing data, entered in SPSS Version 27.0, and cleaned. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous and categorical variables. Results were presented in graphs and tables, with descriptive analysis for significant variables. Descriptive analysis was conducted for significant variables,

Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure questionnaire internal consistency, and Pearson Chi Square was used for categorical variables.

3. Results

The study indicated that 51.3% of respondents were male, with 48.7% female, aged 20-25. Male interns 27.3% in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa were secure placement elsewhere due to non-availability of placement in their affiliated hospitals, while Punjab had a higher proportion of female interns the study revealed that most internees struggled to secure clinical placements from KPK private sector institutions, with 39.6% obtained a placement within 3 months to 1 year after graduation. 24.6% in Private sector institutions of Islamabad (ICT) offered elective areas during placement, most internees were rotated in placement phase less than 8 weeks and 19.8% abided by Council guidelines. Comparatively, Public Sector Hospitals had the lowest mean score for paid internship of 1.18 (SD=1.474), 44.9% were not compensated; in contrast, the mean score in Private Sector Hospitals is a high 3.80 (SD=2.501). Nearly 42.8% male trained from Private Sector Institute waged their expenses by working part-time at another hospital. 45.5% of respondents had shown dissatisfaction (ineffective) on placement from Private Sector institutions of KPK, overall, 49.2% said feedback was poor, and only 13.4% of interns had met their clinical placement objectives, subsequently 44.4% of interns were either unclear if they would achieve the objectives or hesitant Only 1.1% followed the guidelines policy set forth by the Pakistan Nursing Council upon clinical placement.

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Demography	Public		Private	
	Frequency (%)		Frequency (%)	
	Female	Male	Female	Male
Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT)	0	51(27.3)	23 (12.3)	0
Lahore	33 (17.6)	0	26 (13.9)	17 (9.1)
Peshawar	0	0	9 (4.8)	28 (15)
Gender Wise Total	33 (29.3)	51 (60.7)	58 (56.3)	45 (43.9)
Total	84 (44.91)		103 (55.08)	
Gender	Mean		N	Std. Deviation
Female	3.23		91(48.7%)	1.446
Male	2.46		96(51.3%)	2.714
Total	2.83		187	2.219

The study reveals that 51.3% of respondents were male in Peshawar's private institutions, while 48.7% were female in Lahore and Islamabad Capital Territory's public/private sector institutions.

Table 2. Internees and their Clinical Placement

Clinical Placement Institutes	Training Institute							Total
	ICT (Pvt-CON)	Lahore (Pub-CON)	Lahore (Pvt-CON)	Lahore (Pub-CON)	Peshawar (Pvt-CON)	Peshawar (Pvt-CON)	Peshawar (Pvt-CON)	
ICT-Public	0	0	0	0	0	38	13	51
ICT-Private	23	0	0	6	0	0	0	29
Lahore-Public	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	33
Lahore-Private	0	0	37	0	0	0	0	37
Peshawar-Private	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	37

Total	23	33	37	6	37	38	13	187
Mean	1.00	3.00	4.00	1.00	6.00	0.00	0.00	2.660
St- Deviation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.229

The study reveals that a significant number of BS Nursing clinical placements are conducted at public sector institutions in Pakistan, with a majority of males from private sector institutions and a significant proportion of female interns from Punjab's public sector institutions. indicated that 37.3% male and 7.5% of female interns from Punjab's Public Sector Institutions received reciprocal placement at Islamabad Private Sector Teaching Hospital. The p-value in the chi-square test is less than the 0.05 cut-off point, The data's expected count was .93 is larger than the normal, supporting the hypothesis in the chi-square test results.

Table 3. Internees Enrolment Time for Clinical Placement

Clinical Placement Institutions		Enrolment Time			
		1—3 Month	4-6 Month	06-1 Year	Total
ICT-(Islamabad)	Public	0	17	34	51
		0.0%	9.1%	18.2%	27.3%
	Private	6	23	0	29
		3.2%	12.3%	0.0%	15.5%
Lahore-(Punjab)	Public	33	0	0	33
		17.6%	0.0%	0.0%	17.6%
	Private	37	0	0	37
		19.8%	0.0%	0.0%	19.8%
Peshawar-(Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa)	Private	37	0	0	37
		19.8%	0.0%	0.0%	19.8%
	Public	0	0	0	0
		0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Frequency		113	40	34	187
%		60.4%	21.4%	18.2%	100.0%
Mean		0.94	2.80	1.68	1.47
Standard Deviation		0.794	0.405	0.475	1.007

Clinical placements offered meaningful learning experiences, with interns generally taking time from KPK private sector institutions for placement at Public Sector institute of Islamabad. There were sufficient meaningful learning situations on the enrolled in clinical placement with a mean of 1.47 with Standard Deviation 1.007 and the lowest scored 6 month to one year. The data's expected count of 5.27 was indicating it's larger than the normal freedom frequency level, it's larger than the normal, supporting the hypothesis in the chi-square test.

Table 4. Elective Area and Orientation at Clinical Placement Institutions

Clinical Placement Institutions		Elective Area		Orientation		
		Yes	No	Hospital	Supervisor (unit)	Other
ICT- (Islamabad)	Public	8 4.3%	43 23.0%	9 4.8%	0 0.0%	42 22.5%
	Private	19 10.2%	10 5.3%	21 11.2%	2 1.1%	6 3.2%
Lahore- (Punjab)	Public	0 0.0%	33 17.6%	0 0.0%	33 17.6%	0 0.0%
	Private	1 0.5%	36 19.3%	37 19.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
Peshawar- (Khyber- Pakhtunkhwa)	Private	18 9.6%	19 10.2%	7 3.7%	30 16.0%	0 0.0%
	Public	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
Frequency		46	141	74	65	48
%		24.6%	75.4%	39.6%	34.8%	25.7%
Mean		2.85	2.64	2.85	4.32	0.13
Standard Deviation		2.624	2.090	1.890	1.602	0.334

The study found that 24.6% of participants offered elective areas during clinical placement, moreover 19.8% followed Council guidelines, Hence 39.6% received difficult-to-understand oral and written information.

Table 5. Clinical Placement Rotation at Hospitals

Clinical Placement Institutions		Clinical Placement Rotation				According to Council Policy
		less than 16-week	1st 8-weeks or more	less than 8-weeks	Rotation Monthly	
ICT-(Islamabad)	Public	5 2.7%	20 10.7%	21 11.2%	5 2.7%	0 0.0%
	Private	15 8.0%	9 4.8%	4 2.1%	1 0.5%	1 0.5%
Lahore-(Punjab)	Public	0 0.0%	7 3.7%	15 8.0%	11 5.9%	0 0.0%
	Private	2 1.1%	11 5.9%	12 6.4%	12 6.4%	1 0.5%
Peshawar-(Khyber- Pakhtunkhwa)	Private	0 0.0%	14 7.5%	11 5.9%	12 6.4%	0 0.0%
	Public	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
Frequency		22	61	63	41	2
%		11.8%	32.6%	33.7%	21.9%	1.1%
Mean		1.05	2.59	2.59	3.76	2.50
Standard Deviation		1.146	2.390	2.219	1.900	2.121

Clinical Placement rotation was also assessed in accordance to laid down criteria of Nursing Council as shown in Table-05, that only 11.8% were followed Council laid down policies with (SD-1.146). Hence 33.7% with (SD-2.59) were rotated the interneers during 1st rotation of placement less than 8 weeks.21.9% interneers with mean of 3.76(SD=1.900) rotated on monthly basis.

Table 6. Clinical Placement Remuneration and Expenses

Clinical Placement Institutions		Remuneration			Expenses	
		By Institute	Hospital	No	Family / Working at another Hospital	Paid Internship/ Family
ICT-(Islamabad)	Public	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	51 27.3%	31 16.6%	20 10.7%
	Private	0 0.0%	29 15.5%	0 0.0%	14 7.5%	15 8.0%
Lahore-(Punjab)	Public	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	33 17.6%	0 0.0%	1 0.5%
	Private	37 19.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	35 18.7%	1 0.5%
Peshawar-(Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa)	Private	0 0.0%	37 19.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	37 19.8%
	Public	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
Frequency		37	66	84	80	74
%		19.8%	35.3%	44.9%	42.8%	39.6%
Mean		4.00	3.80	1.18	1.93	3.30
Standard Deviation		0.000	2.501	1.474	1.874	2.788

The study found significant differences in clinical placement and remuneration for nursing interneers across study settings. Public Sector Hospitals had the highest percentage of interneers not receiving their remuneration and experiencing difficulties during their internship year, compared to Private Sector Institutions.

Table 7. Clinical Placement Assessment

Statistics					
	Environment	Professional learning	Scope of Practice	Supervision of Interneers	Feedback (Constructive)
Mean	1.87	2.15	1.39	2.41	1.78
Std. Deviation	0.961	0.873	0.85	0.865	0.904
Minimum	0	0	0	1	0
Maximum	4	4	4	5	4
Non-Effective	5.9	1.6	10.7	12.3	8.6
Poor	32.6	24.1	51.9	45.5	25.1
Neutral	33.7	34.8	26.2	32.6	49.2
Effective	24.6	36.9	10.2	8.0	13.9
Very effective	3.2	2.7	1.1	1.6	3.2
	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Note. (Non-Effective-1)/(Poor-2)/(Neither/Nor-3)/(Effective -4)/(Very-Effective -5)

The study found that only 3.2% Mean 1.87(SD=0.961) of the population found the environment conducive for clinical placement, with 36.9% Mean 2.15 (SD=0.873) deeming the professional learning facility effective. The majority of respondents rated the placement program as poor, with 45.5% stating it was ineffective.

Table 8. Chi- Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	111.642 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	119.988	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.426	1	.035
N of Valid Cases	187		

a. 4 cells (26.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.10.

The study found that most internees at public and private sector institutions in Islamabad, Lahore and Peshawar were dissatisfied with their clinical placement atmosphere, with 66.31% dissatisfied and 28.34% neither or nor satisfied. Only 5.4% were satisfied, and 22.27% at public sector institutes from KPK private sector training were in a compromised state, indicating a compromised utility of the compulsory clinical placement.

4. Discussion

This study compares clinical placements of BS Nursing internees in Pakistan's public and private hospitals, addressing concerns about nursing internships being used as extra professional human resources rather than mandatory training, highlighting the importance of a competent clinical learning environment in nursing development.

The quality of the environment for interns is significantly influenced by institutions' capacity to facilitate placements, their liaison with healthcare organizations, and guidelines policy. In addition, Chan in his many evaluations of the clinical learning environment has shown that challenges encountered by students during their clinical learning have made them feel vulnerable and incompetent as students and future nurses.

The study reveals challenges for nursing interns in hospital clinical placement, particularly for male interns in KPK and female interns in Islamabad. Poor staffing, supervision, and overcrowding negatively impact training and placement, emphasizing the need for equal opportunities.

Theoretical learning with in-hand practice is crucial for patient care, and clinical placement in line with Pakistan Nursing Council guidelines offers learning opportunities. However, in Islamabad, female interns are more likely to be placed in private sector hospitals, while male interns are found in public sector hospitals without clinical affiliation. The study shows that 39.6% BS Nursing internees took 3 months to 1 year for obtaining clinical placements, with most internees struggling for internship due to non-availability.

The Nursing Council's criteria for clinical placement rotation were assessed, showing that only 11.8% of internees were placed in accordance, with only 1.1% following the guidelines, indicating a lack of compliance among hospitals. These results concur with Bezuidenhout et al. (1999), Mhlongo (1996), and Mongwe (2001), who observed that the lack of resources and shortage of staff were some of the difficulties faced during clinical teaching. To throw more light on this, Lita et al. (2002) stated that insufficient equipment in the clinical area widened the theory- practice gap by rendering the teaching of student nurses by clinical nurses difficult.

The study indicated that the majority of nursing interns (44.9%) in both private and public sector hospitals do not receive remuneration (paid internship) and face difficulties during their internship year, highlighting the need for improved compensation, expenses, and wages to create competent future nurses. These efforts must be approached collaboratively, where training institutes and clinical placement create circumstances for an encouraging placement environment and contribute to a positive attitude toward internees and their learning needs. (Saarikoski & Leino- Kilpi, 2002). In addition, foster an environment

that nurtures a positive relationship among the regulator and institutions offering clinical placement to enhance the performance of internees on their journey to becoming able to provide high-quality patient care.

The clinical environment of professional learning facilities is hindered by inappropriate supervision and inadequate feedback. Internees generally believe there are sufficient meaningful learning resources, but 36.9% find the facility effective. The placement program is effective at a private sector institute, but 45.5% find it ineffective, with 32.6% describing it as poor and passive. Students' satisfaction in clinical placements is based on clinical support, appreciation, quality guidance, and involvement in practice. 44.4% met objectives, while 36.9% anticipated professional skills in real-world settings.

Therefore, we can conclude that interns' satisfaction levels can significantly be impacted upon by their varying demographic characteristics. A clinical setting rich in learning experiences, but lacking a supportive environment, discourages the learners in seeking experience and results in the loss of learning and growth opportunities (Mabuda, Potgieter & Alberts, 2008). Exclusively, the bar chart in Figure-09 indicated the learning atmosphere of the internees at public and private sectors was (N-187) amongst 44.34% (n-53) from public and private sector institutions Islamabad, Lahore and Peshawar neither/nor satisfied with the clinical placement, Hence, only 5.4% (n-10) were shown satisfaction on the clinical placement learning atmosphere moreover most of the participants from KPK 22.27% (n-42) at public sector institute Islamabad were on state of compromised placement

5. Conclusion

The study indicates that there is a higher number of female interns in Private Sector Hospitals in the Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) compared to KPK Private Sector College male internees 27.3% struggled to find clinical placements after BS Nursing graduation, with only 1.1% following the Nursing Council guidelines. The majority (44.9%) did not receive remuneration (Paid Internship) and had difficulties during their internship year. Ineffective supervision and inadequate feedback hindered professional learning facilities and scope of work. The study can help improve future planning, assessment, monitoring, and surveillance of internship programs, especially for institutions unable to offer clinical placements. Inclusively said that the utility of the obligatory Clinical Placement unvivid and compromised.

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